

Abstract

The present study examines Hayao Miyazaki's film *Howl's Moving Castle* from the perspective of the change in Sophie's perception of time, while also serving as a background text for a later reflexive-methodological study. Its point of departure is the question of how time—which is not directly accessible to the senses—can become perceptible in film. Drawing on the time-sociological approaches of Norbert Elias and Martin Kohli, the analysis argues that it is the destabilization of Sophie's life course and her sudden aging that turn time into a bodily experience: slowing down, fatigue, and physical limitation give a new quality to everyday time-perception. Through the relationship between Sophie and Howl, the paper also places the opposition between youth and old age, as well as outer and inner beauty, within the perspective of time, while the motifs of memory and time travel make the interconnectedness of past, present, and future visible. The study concludes that in the film time appears not as mere passing, but as a qualitative experience saturated with moral and existential meaning.

Bibliographic Information

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Time and Perception in the Anime Film *Howl's Moving Castle*

In what follows I will analyze the anime film *Howl's Moving Castle*, directed by Hayao Miyazaki. My research question is the following: how does Sophie's perception of time change in the course of the film? In my essay I call upon the literature of the sociology of time for assistance.

In his essay *On Time*, Norbert Elias deals with the characteristics of time. "Physicists sometimes claim that they measure time. They use mathematical formulas in which time plays a role as a measure, as a quantity named in words. Yet time can neither be seen, nor felt, nor heard, nor tasted, nor even smelled"¹. Thus, we are also looking for an answer to the question of how the film renders time visible—this concept that cannot be grasped by the senses.

Miyazaki achieves access to the concept of time for both the protagonist and the viewer through a change that takes place in the life course. The first indication of this can be found in the conversation with Lettie. "Do you want to spend your whole life in that hat shop? The shop meant a lot to Father, and I'm the eldest. That's not what I asked; I asked what you want. [...] Live your life and think of yourself too"²! Lettie's warning draws attention to the fact that Sophie does not value the time of her own life and simply carries on the paternal inheritance. The inciting event, the Witch of the Waste's curse, moves the protagonist out of this situation. Sophie's aging overturns her life course. "The life course may be understood as a regulatory system that arranges the temporal dimension of individual life. Today this system is one of the most essential mediating instances between society and the individual. For the individual, the conditions and problems of social structure unfold in 'one's own time'; individual action is adjusted by individual time, and the social consequences of our actions are also registered there"³. Time discloses itself before us through the physical phenomena of aging: a bent, wrinkled, trembling-handed, hoarse old woman.

As she leaves her hometown, she is continually confronted with the consequences of growing old. Her back cracks, she can walk only slowly, and she needs a cane so as not to tire out. Immanuel Kant “merely states that time is an inborn form of experience, thus an unalterable endowment of human nature”⁴. Russian structuralism assigns precisely this task to form: to create “a new perceptibility that does not exist in everyday life”⁵. In the midst of our daily activities, “situations become so habitual that we no longer perceive their specialness, their singularity”⁶. For Sophie, time most certainly slows down, since her bodily sensations continuously signal that she is no longer young. What once came easily now becomes difficult. The moment becomes valuable insofar as, straining her own willpower, she struggles against nature (climbing the hill, her exhausted body).

Miyazaki’s other method is the dialectic of youth and old age, represented by Sophie and Howl. For the protagonist, Howl represents everything she has lost. The boy’s beauty, mobility, and elegant clothes “bewitch” Sophie. By remaining in the castle, she is able to observe directly a (lost) part of herself. According to the formalists, “the task of art is to dismantle automatic seeing, a kind of estrangement, a distancing”⁷. This estrangement becomes evident in Howl’s fit of hysteria. The boy stretches a simple problem out in time. “What is the point of living if I can’t be beautiful?”⁸ Howl’s question deeply affects Sophie, and her vehement reaction is not absent either. “Why are you feeling so sorry for yourself? Imagine it—I was never beautiful in all my life”⁹! After this Sophie goes out into the pouring rain and sobs. It is here that she begins to realize that it is not worth building one’s identity around a quality that can disappear in a moment. This conviction is strengthened in her when she sees the Witch of the Waste “aged back” into oldness. Later she confesses to Howl that she is not beautiful and is only good for cleaning. Howl, however, sees into her interior. “Sophie, you are beautiful”¹⁰! For Sophie has devoted time to keeping life in order: she cleaned his castle, comforted him during his fit, and went to the royal palace in his place. These are signs of inner beauty: kindness and helpfulness. This leads us to the next point.

Miyazaki’s third method is the opposition between outer and inner beauty. It is indispensable to understand “the connections between a social structure caught in a network of time-determinations and a personality structure equipped with a high degree of time-sensitivity and time-discipline”¹¹. Morality can manifest itself only in social context, in time. In the West this is indicated by the well-known folktale saying, one good turn deserves another. In the East the karmic wheel of fate represents it. While human beings lose external beauty in the course of life, their inner beauty and morality accompany them throughout their whole lives. Although Howl entered into an alliance with a demon, which represents desires and selfish feelings, he used his (good) heart to sustain the family hearth. By contrast, the Witch of the Waste was consumed by her own greed. Howl says the following of her: “At first she seemed like an interesting woman and I approached her. Later she frightened me and I fled”¹². Here Sophie again encounters the boy’s soul-seeing perception. By this she comes to regard time not only as a point but as a process. Through Howl’s example the protagonist learns to see the world differently. A further lesson for Sophie comes when she finds out that Howl has sworn himself to the king. In exchange for what they learn at the wizard academy, the king invests in the future of wizard apprentices and expects them to fight for him. Yet Howl fundamentally does not want war and is unwilling to submit to the king. He condemns his own side’s violence just as much as that of the other side. Sophie once again realizes that Howl’s firmness, his moral compass, exceeds even his oath. Other wizards fight as monsters in obedience to the command, and thus their inner corruption becomes their nature and they are unable to transform back into human form. Later, however, Sophie realizes that the same fate awaits Howl. Suliman puts it this way: “If he does not change, he will end like the Witch of the Waste”¹³. Disguised, Howl exposes the sorceress’s secret and her true nature when he declares that she protects her palace with magic and diverts the bombs that then fall on other cities. Suliman takes revenge for this by showing Sophie what kind of being he will become if she does not break Howl’s curse. We may conclude that it becomes clear to the protagonist that

morality is something that changes in time, and that inner corruption finally reveals itself in the outer form as well.

Miyazaki's final method is remembrance. When Sophie grows old under the effect of the curse, the feeling of youth remains sharply alive within her. Her experiences are given a basis for comparison ("Old age is worse than I thought"¹⁴). Howl reminds her, both directly and indirectly, of her former self. As their stories become intertwined, they learn from one another what inner beauty means and how it may be seen in the other. "Story-processes themselves are perceptible. Correspondence shows that people endowed with knowledge process their perceptions. This finds expression in a communicable social symbol, in the concept of 'time,' which within a given society can, with the help of a recognizable sound-pattern, transmit from one person to another an experienceable memory-image that cannot, however, be grasped by the senses"¹⁵. When Sophie travels back in time into Howl's past, the boy's fate becomes experienceable for her as well. "Howl! Calcifer! It's me, Sophie! I know now how I can help you! Wait for me in the future"¹⁶! Sophie realizes that nothing was accidental. The past, the present, and the future are organically connected to one another. Reverie makes it possible for the human being that his or her life course, time-sensitivity, and the process of life be projected onto the imaginary plane called time. Its cyclicity, in turn, is made perceptible and experienceable by the capacity for recollection.

To summarize, we may conclude that "art develops distinctive models of perception [the temporal perception of inner beauty]; these disrupt our habitual relation to the world [the experiences of Sophie and the viewer] and help us to see again [a new illumination of the life course, youth and old age, inner and outer beauty, and remembrance]"¹⁷. Through the rupture that takes place in her own life course, Sophie begins to value the time of her own life. She is compelled to focus on her inner beauty instead of her outer beauty. This becomes intertwined, through Howl, with a temporal view of morality. Time becomes qualitative when we fill it with meaningful activity, and this leads to a "value-emphasized mode of existence"¹⁸.

Notes

1. ELIAS, Norbert. "Az időről." In *Időben élni. Történelmi-szociológiai tanulmányok*, edited by Márta Gellerné Lázár, 15–47. Budapest: Akadémiai, 1990., 15.
2. Hayao MIYAZAKI, *Howl's Moving Castle*, Studio Ghibli, 2004.
3. KOHLI, Martin. "Társadalmi idő és egyéni idő. Az életút a modern társadalom szerkezetváltozásában." In *Időben élni. Történelmi-szociológiai tanulmányok*, edited by Márta Gellerné Lázár, 175–212. Budapest: Akadémiai, 1990.
4. ELIAS, op. cit., 18.
5. BÓKAY, Antal. *Bevezetés az irodalomtudományba*. Budapest: Osiris, 2006.
6. *Ibid.*, 106.
7. *Ibid.*, 106.
8. MIYAZAKI, op. cit.
9. *Ibid.*
10. *Ibid.*
11. ELIAS, op. cit., 20.
12. MIYAZAKI, op. cit.
13. *Ibid.*
14. *Ibid.*
15. ELIAS, op. cit., 23.
16. MIYAZAKI, op. cit.
17. BÓKAY, op. cit., 106.
18. *Ibid.*, 106.

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